

Takayasu Arteritis Presenting with Resistant Hypertension and Aortic Stenosis: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Takayasu arteritis (TA) is a rare large-vessel vasculitis primarily affecting young women. It is characterized by granulomatous inflammation of the aorta and its main branches, leading to stenosis, occlusion, or aneurysm formation. Clinical manifestations are heterogeneous and often delay diagnosis.

Case presentation: We report a 41-year-old female with longstanding arterial hypertension who presented with resistant hypertensive crises, thoracic pain, claudication, and paresthesias. Her medical history included a diagnosis of TA during adolescence, but without consistent follow-up or immunosuppressive treatment. Current imaging revealed significant aortic and iliac artery stenosis. Laboratory and clinical criteria fulfilled the 2022 ACR/EULAR classification for TA. She responded well to intravenous methylprednisolone pulses, followed by methotrexate and oral prednisone maintenance.

KEYWORDS: Takayasu arteritis, large-vessel vasculitis, hypertension, aortic stenosis, immunosuppression, methotrexate.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
25 June 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Takayasu arteritis (TA) is a chronic, idiopathic granulomatous vasculitis that affects large vessels, primarily the aorta and its major branches. The disease predominantly affects women under 40 years old, with a female-to-male ratio of approximately 8:1. Its prevalence ranges from 4.7 to 360 cases per million population, depending on geographic and ethnic background².

The underlying pathogenesis involves a complex interaction of genetic predisposition—particularly HLA-B52—and immune dysregulation, leading to mononuclear infiltration

and granulomatous inflammation of the arterial media³. Clinically, TA progresses from an initial systemic inflammatory phase to a chronic occlusive phase marked by vascular insufficiency, aneurysm formation, or critical stenosis⁴.

Due to its variable presentation and lack of specific serologic markers, diagnosis can be challenging. Updated 2022 ACR/EULAR classification criteria incorporate both clinical and imaging features, including vascular stenosis on angiography or Doppler ultrasound and a total score ≥ 5 for confirmed diagnosis⁵.

Illustration 1. CT angiography demonstrated 65% stenosis of the descending aorta with a 90 mmHg gradient, and stenosis of the iliac arteries.

CASE REPORT

A 41-year-old female presented to our institution on July 8, 2023, with severe thoracic pain, blurry vision, nausea, malaise, and a hypertensive crisis. She reported a long-standing history of elevated blood pressure since the age of 12 and a diagnosis of Takayasu arteritis confirmed via cardiac catheterization in 2016. Despite this, she had remained off immunosuppressive therapy and was only treated with antihypertensive agents: telmisartan/hydrochlorothiazide and nifedipine.

She had experienced recurrent hypertensive crises with blood pressures reaching 220/115 mmHg, accompanied by dyspnea on exertion, distal cyanosis, diaphoresis, and throbbing headaches. She also described intermittent claudication relieved by rest. At admission, her blood pressure differed between arms (151/75 mmHg right, 167/83 mmHg left) and physical exam revealed diminished peripheral pulses and paresthesias in both arms. Femoral pulses were weak, and the Allen test was positive.

Laboratory testing showed mildly elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) (26–33 mm/h) and C reactive protein (CRP) (0.11 mg/dL). Autoimmune panels including antinuclear antibodies (ANA), Anti-double stranded DNA antibodies (anti-dsDNA), rheumatoid factor, Antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA), and antiphospholipid

antibodies were negative. Electrocardiogram (ECG) showed incomplete right bundle branch block and T-wave inversion. Echocardiography revealed concentric left ventricular hypertrophy with preserved ejection fraction and bicuspid aortic valve with mild regurgitation.

Computerized tomography (CT) angiography demonstrated 65% stenosis of the descending aorta with a 90 mmHg gradient, and stenosis of the iliac arteries. Carotid Doppler ultrasound showed bilateral intima-media thickening (1.0–1.3 mm). The findings met the 2022 ACR/EULAR classification score for Takayasu arteritis (≥ 5 points)⁵.

She was treated with intravenous methylprednisolone 500 mg for 3 days, followed by oral prednisone 50 mg/day and weekly methotrexate (20 mg) with folic acid. Antihypertensive therapy was optimized. She experienced significant symptom improvement and was discharged under outpatient rheumatology and cardiology follow-up. Tuberculosis screening was negative, and vaccinations for pneumococcus and influenza were administered. Methotrexate was discontinued in March 2024, and she continues on low-dose prednisone (5 mg/day).

DISCUSSION

This case underscores the insidious nature of Takayasu arteritis, which often presents years before diagnosis or treatment is initiated. Our patient had a prior diagnosis of TA but remained off immunosuppressive therapy, which likely contributed to progressive arterial stenosis.

Current guidelines recommend initiating treatment with high-dose corticosteroids to induce remission, ideally combined with conventional immunosuppressants such as methotrexate or azathioprine⁶. In refractory cases, biologics like tocilizumab or tumoral necrosis factor inhibitors may be considered⁶. Long-term therapy aims to prevent vascular remodeling and ischemic complications.

Although acute phase reactants such as ESR and CRP are helpful, they lack sensitivity and specificity. Imaging remains the cornerstone for diagnosis and monitoring. Modalities such as Positron Emission Tomography (PET), Magnetic resonance angiography, or Doppler ultrasound can reveal vessel wall inflammation, though optimal frequency of follow-up imaging is yet to be standardized⁷.

TA may lead to severe complications including aortic aneurysm, valvular dysfunction, myocardial infarction, and stroke. Cardiovascular mortality remains significant, although 5-year survival with adequate treatment exceeds 85%⁸.

CONCLUSION

This case illustrates the importance of long-term follow-up and multidisciplinary management in patients with Takayasu arteritis. Despite early diagnosis, lack of immunosuppressive therapy led to disease progression. Prompt treatment with steroids and disease-modifying agents is essential to prevent irreversible vascular damage. Awareness of classification

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criteria and imaging features is vital for early detection and improved outcomes.

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